

Fundamental Human Rights and Gender Violence in Greece

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Introduction

Gender violence is distinguished as a phenomenon that is in the human entity, which produces crucial effects. From antiquity to the present day there are reports, which demonstrate the phenomenon of violence. The range of references ranges from ancient Greek texts to religious texts, such as those made through the Old Testament. (Katsos, 2019). Gender-based violence is a social problem and is characterized as a crime (Government Gazette 232/A/24-10-2006, 2006) whether it is verbal, physical or mental health. The purpose of any favored society is to seek to abolish inequalities, social exclusion and to highlight fundamental human rights, dignity and security. Pillars, through which the factors are highlighted, for the starting point of a safe and vision of a society, as the dignity of man does not need any thought of violation. On the contrary, the ultimate goal is to establish rights in the context of freedoms and security (Map of the Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2012).

1. Fundamental Human Rights. Ethics and Values

Human rights and dignity are the foundation upon which "freedom, justice, and peace in the world rest" (Minister of Justice, Human Rights-National Action Plan, 2014). In Aristotelian thought, the individual and the political good are identified. In this way, not only the possibility of taking responsibility is offered, but also the possibility of deciding fairly by helping people to conquer the good (Kopidakis et al., 2013). A conquest that man seeks through freedom and justice for his personal and social progress, for the development and conquest of his personal freedom. However, this freedom is affected and limited by the manifestations of violence (Petalia, 2018).

Historically throughout the centuries, man seeks freedom and the securing of fundamental rights, just as justice has always been one of the most important moral values (Stamboulis, 2020). And these basic moral values have now penetrated "into the consciousness of the individual", which if violated causes an effervescence in the mental mechanism (Yotsa, 2006).

This conscious placement of basic moral values in the hierarchical scale of human values found its historical expression in the French Revolution of 1789 with the motto "Liberty, Equality, Fraternity" (Katsoulakos et al. 2019). The Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen, as an outcome of the Revolution of the French people, was a milestone in securing and recognizing rights. (Vlachopoulos, 2017). Under this influence, not only the various legal texts but also the European Constitutions themselves were shaped in such a way, in which, according to Vlachopoulos (2017), "a more humanistic character" was expressed.

In our time, human value is an inviolable principle, both in the Constitution of Greece and in International Law (Vlachopoulos, 2017). Fundamental Rights have upgraded their role, within which there is now a "protective dimension". A dimension in which the Rule of Law can intervene by ensuring the freedom and dignity of its citizens through the respect, protection and development of Fundamental Rights (Vlachopoulos, 2017). According to the Constitution of Greece in Part II, Individual and Social Rights in Article 25 "1. The rights of man as an individual and as a member of society and the principle of the social rule of law are guaranteed by the State. All state bodies are required to ensure their unhindered and effective exercise. These rights also apply to the relationships between individuals to which they apply. 2. The recognition and protection of the fundamental inalienable rights of man by the State aims at the realization of social progress within freedom and justice" (Karatza, 2002).

Within a more general framework man seeks the existence of a world, which will be surrounded by strong foundations, where the triptych of Family, Culture, Society will look forward to the respect of life itself. In a world where it will be freely governed by the ancient Greek "metron", as it was expressed in the brightest fruits of the ancient Greek intellect. (Kechagias, 2020).

As mentioned above, the first pillar and basic institution in society is the family, which according to (Athanasoula - Reppa et al., 2000) A related reference to this is also found in Article 21 par. 1 of the Constitution, where "the family is as the foundation of the preservation and promotion of the Nation, as well as marriage, motherhood and childhood are under the protection of the State" (Vlachopoulos, 2017).

The second pillar and important part for progress and evolution is the cultivation (education) of man (Vekris et al., 2019). Based on the human being and society itself, education

has the potential to highlight and contribute to the personality of each individual, laying the foundations for the promotion of "human rights and fundamental rights" (Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948). The same reasoning can be seen in Bikos' view, where knowledge can not only determine choices, but also lay the foundations for both life attitudes and behaviors that can shape life as a whole (Bikos, 2011). Life through evolution, which needs to be practical and complete, contains an important part, which according to Aristotle, is defined as virtue. Virtue is gained after persistence and continuous exercise and which in the Aristotelian book "Nicomachean Ethics", is categorized into intellectual and moral (Salamouras, 2017). From these moral virtues are acquired, they do not oppose human nature and are developed on the one hand through teaching and on the other through habit (Vekris, et al., 2019). In this way it is suggested that moral virtues are not innate. These are one of the contexts that lead to knowledge, as well as the opposite: that knowledge leads to ethics (Staboulis, 2020).

Third Pillar is society itself. Societies change rapidly every day due to challenges from external factors but also from their internal functioning (Athanasoula-Reppa et al. 2000) Through daily challenges and threats every civil society maintains the expectation but also the responsibility that "all people are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience, and ought to treat one another in a spirit of brotherhood" (Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948).

For his part, the legislator raised the term "individual and social rights" in 1975. (Chrysogonos & Vlachopoulos, 2017) Subsequently, additional terms were formulated which referred to constitutional freedoms and constitutional rights, as well as fundamental and human rights (Chrysogonos & Vlachopoulos, 2017). The first international document in which the framework of equal rights for men and women was formulated in precise terms was the Charter of the United Nations, which states "faith in Fundamental Human Rights, in the dignity and worth of man, in the equal rights of men and women , of great and small nations" (United Nations, 1948). Four decades later, in 1992, the United Nations incorporated the definition of the use of violence into the corresponding definition of gender discrimination in Article 1 of the CEDAW Convention (Convention of the Elimination for all Discrimination Against Women) (Miloni, 2009).

2. The legal framework on domestic violence in Greece

The national and European legislation are a cornerstone in the life of the European citizen regardless of his economic, physical and also spiritual development. And this by contributing

through unity and respect for the freedom of fellow human beings to the abolition of inequalities and social exclusion and by strengthening dignity and human rights, through the respective provisions (to deal with violence). The "cooperation" of the national and European legislations is distinguished until today in the twenty-first century, through the Istanbul Convention.

The Istanbul Convention, which was ratified in 2011, was the legislative core for dealing with violence against women and the beginning of European and not only legislation for the respect of human rights through the "harmonization of all national legislation that each state has, as well as developing administrative practices" (EL.AS., 2021). It should be noted that the importance of human rights is also mentioned in the United Nations Convention, which was ratified by the Hellenic Parliament in 1989 and concerns the elimination of any form of discrimination against women (EtK, 1989). In the First part, Article 1, the purpose of the Convention is mentioned, which is human rights, equality. Equality between "men and women, regardless of marital status." (EtK, 1989). Domestic violence has not been researched in a systematic manner in Greece. More importantly, the absence of a specific law until 2006 has caused confusion about definitions and actions that should be taken. In Greek legislation, violence against women refers to provisions that concern "crimes against the life and integrity of the individual, as well as crimes against the personal freedom of honor and personality of the individual, as well as crimes against sexual freedom" (Sandali, 2001). Furthermore, according to Chrysogono and Vlachopoulos, gender equality "establishes the obligation of the state to take measures both for legal reasons and for the social life in which inequalities exist". (Chrysogonos & Vlachopoulos, 2017). Likewise, according to the Greek State (Ministry of Justice, Sanction of the Criminal Code, 2019) "the principle of the social state", which through the Constitution has been enshrined and highlighted "the indivisibility of freedom and social justice" aims strengthening respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms.

Many of the internationally recognized human rights standards are vested in the Greek Constitution. Article 2 paragraph 1 explicitly declares: "*Respect and protection of the value of the human being constitute the primary obligations of the State*" (Karatzas, 2002). Also in Article 25 paragraphs 1 and 2 of the Constitution states: "*1. The rights of man as an individual and as a member of the society and the principle of the constitutional welfare state are guaranteed by the State. All agents of the State shall be obliged to ensure the unhindered and effective exercise thereof. These principles also apply to relations between private individuals to which they pertain. Restrictions of any kind which, according to the Constitution, may be imposed upon these rights should be provided either directly by the Constitution or by the law, in case a reservation exists in the latter's favor, and should respect the principle of proportionality. 2. The recognition and*

*protection of the fundamental and inalienable rights of man by the State aims at the achievement of social progress in freedom and justice.”*¹ In Part II, Individual and Social Rights and Article 4, there is a reference to the equality of Greek men and women, both having equal rights and obligations (Chrysogonos & Vlachopoulos, 2017). The constitutional Article 5 par. 2 mentions the inalienable right to life as a value (Vlachopoulos, 2017) whereby "those who are in the Greek territory enjoy the protection of their life, honor and freedom, without distinction of nationality, race, language and religious or political beliefs". (Karatza, 2002). Similarly, in this Article and in paragraph 3 it is stated that "personal freedom is a human right and therefore its violation is not understood" (Vlachopoulos, 2017).

Also, the regulations of the EU have, under certain conditions, direct effect in the Greek legal order and can be invoked before Greek courts without having needed neither ratification by Parliament, nor transformation into national law nor any further conditions. Law 1342/1983 implements the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women into Greek law and contains a full translation of the Convention into Greek. It should be noted that Law 1342/1983 has never be invoked by a Greek court.

Until the introduction of the *Law on Combating Domestic Violence 2006* (3500/2006), Greece did not have in the penal code a law specifically relating to domestic violence/intimate partner violence. The law sets the definition of the domestic violence, recognizes domestic violence as a particular crime and provides for certain penalties. More specifically, the 2006 law “*provides for prosecution by force of law, without the need for a victim to press charges, for all domestic violence crimes. Penalties range from two to 10 years imprisonment, depending on the gravity of the crime*” (Government Gazette 232/A/24-10-2006, 2006).

Similarly, in Article 7 "Domestic illegal violence and threat" the following are defined: "1. The member of the family who forces another member using violence or threat with great and immediate danger in an act, omission or tolerance without the victim being obliged to do so shall be punished by imprisonment of at least six months, regardless of whether the threatened harm is directed against the victim himself or one of his relatives within the meaning of case b of article 13 of the Criminal Code. 2. The family member who causes fear or anxiety to another family member, by threatening him with Violence or other illegal act or omission, shall be punished by imprisonment" (Legislation, 2020). Moreover, the law is providing for the removal of a violent

¹ Please note that in Greek it says, “the right of human” (anthropos) instead of “the right of man.” The above constitutional provisions are interpreted as obliging the State to take appropriate legislative and administrative measures to guarantee the unhindered exercise of individual rights, including the protection of such rights from acts of private individuals against one another (P.D. Dagtoglou (1991). *Constitutional Law, Individual Rights*, vol. 1, Athens: Sakkoulas, p. 101 and 199). Thus, the State is obliged to adopt relevant legal and administrative requirements regulating the exercise and protection of such rights within society.

spouse from the marital home, as well as the necessary moral and material assistance to the victims by institutions that have been set up for that reason. Last but not least, marital rape is recognized as a punishable criminal offence against the person and personal freedom.

While welcoming the law, the United Nations Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) has expressed concern regarding the provision within the law of encouraging mediation as a first step between the victim and the abuser: The Committee is concerned that the availability of the mediation procedure in criminal cases for certain types of domestic violence at the instance of the prosecutor may lead to the re-victimization of women who have suffered violence. Also, the Committee recommends that the State party carry out studies and monitor closely the Law on Combating Domestic Violence, particularly its mediation procedure, in order to ensure that the legislation is implemented in a way that respects and promotes women's human rights and does not lead to perpetrators escaping punishment. The Committee calls on the State party to put in place training measures for judges who conduct mediation in criminal proceedings for domestic violence cases so as to enhance their capacity to deal with violence against women in a gender-sensitive manner.²

According to the US Department of State, the 2006 law “provides for prosecution by force of law, without the need for a victim to press charges, for all domestic violence crimes. Penalties range from two to 10 years’ imprisonment, depending on the gravity of the crime.” Despite this provision, “only a small fraction” of those cases registered with police “reached trial”.³

Commenting on Law 3500/2006, the Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies (MIGS) states that judicial mediation is for “minor crimes of domestic violence”; however, the MIGS does not specify what constitutes a minor crime in the context of domestic violence. MIGS states that “brutal behavior” is defined as acts that “result in severe physical and mental injuries and/or damage to the victim’s health, as well as cases involving severe threats and coercion”. Such cases are required by the 2006 law to be “punished much more harshly”. MIGS reported that in cases of judicial mediation, a perpetrator is “instructed to make amends for his behavior and to follow a special advisory and therapeutic programme”. Should this programme fail, “the perpetrator will be prosecuted for flagrant violation of the law”.⁴

² UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) 2007, *UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women: Concluding Comments, Greece*, CEDAW/C/GRC/CO/6, 2 February, pp.3-4. See <http://www.unhcr.org/refworld/docid/45f6cfc52.html>. Accessed 24 August 2022.

³ US Department of State 2011, *Country Reports on Human Rights Practices 2010 – Greece*, 8 April, Section 5

⁴ Mediterranean Institute of Gender Studies 2008, *Intercultural Dialogue on Violence against Women*, Dipartimento Per Le Parti Opportunita website p.35 (<http://www.retepariopportunita.it/RetePariOpportunita/UserFiles/news/interculturaldialogueonviolenceagainstwomenresourcebook1162008all.pdf>). Accessed 24 August 2022

A 2008 report by the Daphne Programme of the European Commission states that despite the introduction of the 2006 law, “the term „violence against women” is not used in the Greek Penal Code”.⁵ In 2011, the World Organization Against Torture recommended that the 2006 Law “be changed in order to address violence against women”.⁶

In May 2011, Greece signed the Council of Europe’s *Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence*.⁷ Article 4.1 of the Convention states that: “Parties shall take the necessary legislative and other measures to promote and protect the right for everyone, particularly women, to live free from violence in both the public and the private sphere”.⁸ Article 18.1 states: Parties shall take the necessary legislative or other measures to protect all victims from any further acts of violence.⁹

During last year, Greece has changed governments three times. It is not clear as to what priority gender equality and issues relating to domestic violence have with the current Greek administration.

3. Supportive Structures. The case of Greece during the period 2006-2012

It has been estimated, however, that until 2002, 83% of Greek women has suffered from some form of domestic abuse, either psychological or physical. To the old school Greek mentality, a slap in the face is a form of emotional communication for both sexes; and the Mediterranean temperament excuses such gestures as an indication of passion. The Greek Research Center on Equality Matters (KETHI) issued an informative booklet on violence against women in 2000, where it stressed that violence against women is not caused by poverty and unemployment. Rather, the cause for violence against women is the fact that Greek society does not recognize substantial equality between men and women in everyday life. The relationships amongst the two sexes are relationships of power and subordination, not of companionship and respect. Thus, violence against women is easily excused, at least more than any other form of

⁵ Kane, J. (2008). *Daphne Booklet: Family Violence*, European Commission website, July, p.13 (<http://ec.europa.eu/justicehome/daphnetoolkit/files/others/booklets/05daphnebooklet5en.pdf>) Accessed 24 August 2022

⁶ World Organisation Against Torture (2011) *State Violence in Greece: An Alternative Report to the United Nations Committee Against Torture*, 20 October. (<http://www.unhcr.org/refworld/docid/4ec656bc2html>). Accessed 24 August 2022

⁷ An interactive map of the Council of Europe website indicates that Greece is a signatory. *Interactive Map: Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence Signatories* (<http://www.coe.int/t/dghl/standardsetting/convention-violence/source/flash/map/mapen.htm>). Accessed 26 August 2022.

⁸ Council of Europe 2011, *Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence*, 12 April, article 4.1 (<http://www.coe.int/t/dghl/standardsetting/convention-violence/texts/Conventionen.pdf>). Accessed 24 August 2022.

⁹ Council of Europe 2011, *Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence*, 12 April, article 18.1 (<http://www.coe.int/t/dghl/standardsetting/convention-violence/texts/Conventionen.pdf>). Accessed 24 August 2022.

violence is excused, and many times the victim is accused of provoking such violence. Men learn that it is their right to control the mind, heart and life of their women, and learn to feel security when their companion is dependent and submitted. A completely independent female companion breeds insecurity since it is not her priority to make a man happy. Women themselves learn to be submissive, to be patient with violence, to remain silent and not demanding. As a result, there is a lack of solidarity among women who experience violence that reinforces inactivity against violence.¹⁰

According to academic research, a Greek woman will report domestic violence to the police for the first time, after experiencing on average 35 incidents of violence. This figure is an indication of the situation: 90%-95% of the women incarcerated in Greek prisons for killing their husbands, committed the crime due to suffering long-term violence from their spouses. The situation now is hopeful since 93% of the Greeks men state that domestic violence against women is unacceptable and should always punished by law. Before a decade and in the same question the positive answers were just 25%!

Domestic violence, including spousal abuse and rape,¹¹ continued to be a problem. According with the nongovernmental organization (NGO) “WIN Hellas”

- 1 in 4 women in Greece has, or will be, a victim of abuse at some point in her life.
- 28% of women who have been victims of abuse in the past continue to be victims in future relationships.
- 1 in 2 women murdered in Greece are murdered by their spouse or partner.
- 63% of victims of domestic abuse have children.
- Approximately 80% of the victims that reach out for help are in the age bracket of 25-54, which is considered the most productive years of a woman’s life.
- About a quarter of women in Greece have experienced either physical or sexual violence since the age of 15, according to a survey by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights.

Also, the number of female victims in domestic violence cases reported to police increased 72 percent, from 1,186 in 2010 to 2,043 in 2012.¹² The report adds Greece’s DV hotline has received more than 12,300 calls since March 2011. The 2013 State Department’s Human

¹⁰ Research Center on Equality Matters/KETHI. 2000. *Break the Silence*. Athens.

¹¹ In Greece spousal rape is a crime. Medical, psychological, social, and legal support was usually available to spousal rape victims from the government and NGOs.

¹² Em. Bartha (2013). “Greek police report spike in domestic abuse cases.” *Thomson Reuters Foundation*, 12/ 2/2013.

Rights report for Greece notes, “. . .ten women were killed in domestic violence incidents in 2011, five in 2012, and eight in the first 11 months of the year [2013].”¹³

The General Secretariat for Gender Equality (GSGE), an independent government agency, reported that domestic violence was common and developed policies to combat it such as encouraging and empowering the victims to report domestic violence and offering shelter services to victims. The law provides for the prosecution of all domestic violence crimes without the need for a victim to press charges. Penalties range from two to ten years’ imprisonment, depending on the gravity of the crime. The GSGE estimated that only 6 to 10% of domestic violence victims contacted the police and only a small fraction of those complaints went to trial. The GSGE received 5,057 calls from victims of domestic violence between March 2011 (when it established a women’s abuse hotline) and May 2012.

The GSGE, in cooperation with the Ministry of Citizen Protection, trained police on working with domestic violence victims. NGOs reported that courts were lenient to male offenders in domestic violence cases. Police stations generally had a manual on how police should treat victims of domestic violence. The GSGE provided counseling and assistance to domestic violence victims. Two GSGE shelters for battered women and their children in Athens and Piraeus offered services including legal and psychological help. The GSGE operated a 24-hour emergency telephone hotline for abused women, and the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity operated a hotline providing referrals and psychological counseling for victims. The municipality of Athens, the Greek Orthodox Church, and a variety of NGOs also operated shelters and walk-in centers, providing counseling and assistance to victims.

The police recorded 80 spousal rapes during the year 2012, compared with 84 in 2011. Government statistics on the extent of domestic violence, and spousal abuse were either unavailable or outdated. Data on prosecutions, convictions, and prison sentences for rape and domestic violence crimes were unavailable.

Compounding the domestic violence problem, although we stress it is not the root source of it, is Greece’s unprecedented economic crisis. Unemployment in Greece hovers at 27% and among youth it is a staggering 62.5%.¹⁴ According to a Thomson Reuters report, experts believe it could be pushing more men to violence while leaving women no choice but to stay with their spouses or partners; “*men who feel that their masculinity is threatened by unemployment have*

¹³ State Department’s Human Rights (2013). Report for Greece (<http://www.state.gov/j/drl/rls/hrrpt/humanrightsreport/index.htm?year=2013&dclid=220284>). Accessed 24 August 2022.

¹⁴ D. Thompson (2013). “Europe’s Record Youth Unemployment: The Scariest Graph in the World Just Got Scariest.” *The Atlantic*, 05/31/2013.

become increasingly abusive towards women...”.¹⁵ The Guardian also published a piece on how women are disproportionately impacted by Greece’s economic crisis, including facing a rise in domestic violence.¹⁶

Epilogue

Despite the steps towards the protection of Fundamental Human Rights and human dignity, they are still not adequately protected even today, in the twenty-first century (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2019). Despite the declarations, conventions, laws concerning Fundamental Human Rights, inequality, gender-based violence, abuse, social exclusion continue to exist. Having reached the twenty-first century, the necessity for highlighting Fundamental Human Rights and the conditions in the family, educational and general environment of society, concerning issues of gender-based violence (homicide, domestic violence, sexual abuse) continues to be even more relevant. Gender-based violence is a permanent "sensitive, contemporary and topical" concern in society (Sarri & Bikos, 2020).

¹⁵ L. Woestman & K. Kinoti (2011). *The Effects of The Global Economic Crisis and Structural Adjustment On Women And Gender Relations In Greece: First Wave*, AWID website, 15 April <http://www.awid.org/News-Analysis/Friday-Files/The-Effects-of-the-Global-Economic-Crisis-and-Structural-Adjustment-on-Women-and-Gender-Relations-in-Greece-First-Wave>. Accessed 16 August 2022.

¹⁶ The Guardian (2012). “How women are disproportionately impacted by Greece’s economic crisis” (<http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/greek-election-blog-2012/2012/jun/15/greek-crisis-women-especially-hard>).

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